

FlowQuery: AI-Assisted Visual Boolean Query Construction for Iterative Patent Search Development

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Abstract

Patent search requires precise and often complex Boolean query construction to retrieve relevant prior art across vast, linguistically diverse datasets. This process remains cognitively demanding and error-prone, with traditional text-based interfaces offering little support for iterative refinement or semantic exploration. We present a novel system that reimagines patent search as an interactive, visual process combining symbolic precision with semantic guidance. Our system features a graphical Boolean query editor, AI-assisted refinement workflows, vector-based semantic clustering, and drag-and-drop interactivity from results to query space. The visual interface enhances transparency by eliminating ambiguities in operator precedence and supporting nested, foldable logic containers. Crucially, our system reduces friction in the discovery and refinement loop: users can drag significant terms, date ranges, and even semantic clusters directly from search results into structured queries. These features promote a fluid interaction model, where exploratory actions yield immediate, actionable refinements. The system supports integration with varied backend search engines via minimal adaptation, ensuring wide applicability. By bridging the gap between exploratory search and legal-grade precision, our approach significantly improves usability, transparency, and effectiveness in patent information retrieval. This paper outlines the system's architecture, interaction model, and potential to reshape workflows for legal and technical users alike.

Keywords

Patent Search, Boolean Query Formulation, Visual Query Interfaces, AI-assisted Search, Semantic Clustering, Query Refinement

1. Introduction

Patent search plays a pivotal role in the realm of intellectual property (IP) management and significantly impacts a wide array of critical business decisions including patentability assessments, freedom-to-operate (FTO) analyses, competitive intelligence gathering, technological trend monitoring, and strategic innovation planning. These diverse applications underscore the importance of efficiently retrieving precise and relevant patent documentation. Achieving this precision, however, requires the construction of carefully formulated Boolean queries designed to match exact linguistic patterns or technological features within vast and heterogeneous patent databases.

Despite their importance and widespread use, traditional patent search methodologies present considerable challenges due to their inherent complexity and the cognitive demand they impose on users. Crafting effective Boolean queries necessitates deep familiarity with technical vocabulary, domain-specific jargon, and varying linguistic nuances such as synonyms, acronyms, abbreviations, and alternative phraseology. Users must also navigate the complexities associated with logical query structures, operator precedence rules, and platform-specific syntactic variations. This high cognitive load often results in significant time investment, increased probability of human error, reduced search accuracy, and a high barrier to entry for novice users or professionals transitioning between different platforms.

Compounding these intrinsic challenges, existing patent search interfaces primarily rely on textual representations of Boolean logic, frequently exacerbating user confusion and ambiguity. The lack of visual clarity and intuitive structuring in traditional text-based query systems amplifies the difficulty in accurately interpreting operator precedence

and query logic, leading to inconsistent and unintended search outcomes. Furthermore, the absence of standardized query syntax and behavior across different patent databases exacerbates user difficulties, significantly hampering cross-platform portability. Consequently, patent searchers often face redundant efforts in manually reconstructing and translating queries for different platforms, leading to inefficiencies and potential inaccuracies in search execution.

While semantic search methods utilizing vector embeddings and machine learning algorithms have emerged to address some limitations of traditional keyword-based searches, they often lack the specificity, transparency, and auditability essential for legal analyses such as infringement or invalidity assessments. Purely semantic methods tend to sacrifice precision in favor of exploratory recall, making them suboptimal for strict legal contexts where explicit and reproducible search logic is necessary for defensibility and compliance. Additionally, vector embeddings are only as good as their training data, which can mean they have no awareness of information like new category codes or product names that are potential subjects of interest.

To effectively bridge the gap between traditional Boolean search precision and the exploratory flexibility of semantic techniques, we propose an integrated visual and AI-assisted patent search system. Our approach combines a visual Boolean query editor for intuitive and transparent query construction, context-sensitive query expansion driven by interactive data analytics, semantic clustering via vector embeddings for exploratory refinement, and iterative query optimization using advanced AI methods. The system is designed to integrate seamlessly with various backend search engines through minimal extensions or modifications, ensuring robust cross-platform compatibility and significantly reducing redundant manual effort.

In this paper, we describe the architecture, functionality, and key features of our system, emphasizing the improvements in usability, interpretability, efficiency, and portability it brings to patent search workflows. We also discuss relevant literature and contextualize our contributions within the broader landscape of patent search and information re-

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retrieval, setting the stage for subsequent detailed exploration.

2. Related Work

Patent search systems have evolved through visual query builders and AI assistance to address the unique challenges of prior art search. Early work such as Filter/Flow by Young and Shneiderman [1] introduced graphical representations of Boolean queries, demonstrating that visual metaphors like flowing filters could enhance comprehension and reduce cognitive load compared to traditional text-based query construction. Later, visual approaches like 2Dsearch [2], which represent Boolean logic graphically, and systems such as Payandeh et al.'s mobile interface [3], which support exploratory search via drag-and-drop query refinement, aim to reduce cognitive load and improve query clarity over text-based interfaces. However, these systems typically offer limited interaction with search results and do not make use of modern developments like vector-embeddings when composing searches.

AI-assisted methods like Adaptive Search Query Generation [4] leverage machine learning for query optimization. Domain-specific tools like pybool_ir [5] focus on Boolean query handling for specialized contexts. The Comprehensive Survey on AI-based Methods for Patents [6] highlights AI's role in semantic search yet notes transparency limitations. These approaches address key challenges in search strategy formulation but fall short in meeting patent search's unique demands for transparency, interactivity, and domain-specific adaptability.

Current systems face three key limitations: (1) inadequate handling of complex hierarchical query structures, (2) insufficient integration between Boolean precision and semantic exploration, and (3) limited transparency in result matching.

FlowQuery addresses these gaps through three innovations: nested foldable logic containers that manage complex queries (50+ clauses); seamless integration of Boolean logic with vector-based semantic clustering through drag-and-drop interactions, surpassing siloed modalities [7, 8]; and clause-level matching transparency with interactive Sankey diagrams addresses the "black box" issue, aligning with [9]'s call for transparency. Query refinement is accelerated by enabling direct dragging of new discoveries in search results into the FlowQuery editor—making all displayed results actionable.

Unlike previous approaches that treat visual construction, AI collaboration, and semantic exploration as separate features, FlowQuery integrates them as interdependent components—maintaining Boolean logic as the foundation while enhancing it through modern interaction paradigms and machine learning to achieve both legal-grade precision and exploratory flexibility with an emphasis on direct manipulation.

3. System description

The system provides a graphical tool for editing the complex queries often found in patent search. An intuitive flow-based arrangement of Boolean query clauses is used, with horizontal sequences for conjunctions and vertical groupings for disjunctions. This reduces cognitive load by aligning query structure with innate visual processing, allowing users to interpret complex logic more efficiently than with textual representations.

Figure 1: Visual query builder interface showing horizontal conjunction chains and vertical disjunction groups

The visual representation provides much-needed transparency - unlike mathematics, the field of search has no standard for interpreting Boolean operator precedence and a simple text expression like "dog AND lead OR leash" without brackets can be interpreted differently by different search engines. The graphical representation removes ambiguity.

3.1. Graphical editor content management

Boolean AND/OR/NOT containers can be nested arbitrarily with the ability to "fold away" large sections, much like a modern software editor allows programmers to fold sections of code to manage complexity.

3.1.1. Drag and drop

Direct manipulation can be used to drag and drop clauses to refine the query including:

- Reorganising existing clauses:
 - Dragging a clause from one query container to another (e.g. change an ORed item to an AND)
 - Dragging a clause on top of another to make a new container (e.g. combine two items as an AND)
- Adding new clauses from search results:
 - Dragging from an individual document (e.g. an IPC code discovered in a matching document)
 - Dragging from analytical summaries (e.g. the vector embedding representing a cluster of related patents)

3.1.2. Context-sensitive support for new clauses

The "plus" icons in the editor serve as entry points for adding new clauses—users can either click to create a new clause or drag an existing one onto them to insert it into the logic flow. The choice of which plus icon in the query is used provides important context:

- The position context defines if the new clause will be used to expand matches (as an OR) or narrow (using AND/NOT)
- The position context guides the selection of new value choices, only suggesting relevant clauses that are known to exist in the subset of documents at that point in the query flow. There is little point suggesting clauses that won't match anything.

3.1.3. Refining queries with keyword suggestion

The system provides context-sensitive suggestions for text-based queries when adding new clauses. A statistical analysis of search results matching the current query is undertaken and provides a source of suggestions for query expansion.

Figure 2: A search for the IPC category code A01K27/003 yields search results with statistically significant keywords and phrases.

3.1.4. Supporting the query refinement workflow

"Mute" and "Solo" functions allow searchers to test and refine individual elements' matching behavior in isolation. The mute and solo functions are borrowed from practices in the field of music production where all software and hardware mixing desks are expected to support these features. Like searchers composing queries, music producers need to focus on refining individual tracks or groups of tracks in isolation and then examine how these behave in concert with all other tracks.

Figure 3: The user is temporarily muting the group of clauses relating to "retracting" dog leads in order to examine matching behaviour of other terms.

In our system, mute and solo operations can apply to individual "leaf" level clauses or groups of clauses.

3.2. Support for multiple clause types

The Boolean graphical editor acts as the organising framework for assembling combinations of the many different clause types popular with search engines and databases. The system includes support for nesting any combinations of Term, Prefix, Phrase, Fuzzy, RegEx, Geo, Range, Vector, and ComplexPhrase query clause types.

Each clause in the editor can be opened to reveal a type-specific editor panel for editing detailed properties.

"Complex phrase" queries have an editing panel that mirrors the horizontal and vertical layout of the Boolean editor but this time the left-to-right arrangement implies "AND NEAR" condition rather than simply "AND".

Figure 4: Example panel for changing the "editDistance" property for a fuzzy query.

Figure 5: A search for the words dog or pet directly preceding the words lead or leash.

3.3. Legacy query language support

Many patent searchers are familiar with text-based queries such as the Lucene query string syntax¹ with its AND/OR and bracket operators used in many systems.

The system supports parsing any of these expressions into the graphical editor for further refinement. While we have argued text is a poor system for managing complex Boolean queries, this syntax remains a valuable form of data entry in the system for shorter expressions, e.g. making it quick to enter a simple phrase query by using quotes.

The system can convert graphical queries back to Lucene query syntax string - with some caveats. Lucene syntax is a subset of the system's search capabilities so certain graphical clause types have no counterpart in the Lucene query syntax, for example:

- Unsupported clause types:
 - Geographic queries
 - Vector queries
 - Complex phrases
- Unsupported clause options:
 - Regular expression case sensitivity flags

3.4. Vector clustering

The system provides the means for users to interactively cluster results² based on similarity. This helps identify clusters of related patents that are of interest and each cluster produces a tangible vector embedding that can be dragged as a new query clause.

A slider is used to group results into a small number of loosely related groups or a high number of very specific

¹<https://lucene.apache.org/core>

²<https://qry.codes>

Figure 6: Top results grouped into related clusters such as dog leashes with some kind of illumination and those made from rubber.

topics - or somewhere in between. Each document has a vector embedding that is used to compute similarity for clustering. Document vectors in a cluster are averaged to produce the centerpoint vector of a cluster for potential use in querying. These prove to be very effective in capturing the meaning of a topic used in a search.

3.5. Matching transparency for humans and more

The system provides clause-level feedback on which clauses in the Boolean query are matching or not. Figure 7 illustrates this with a visual example, where a non-matching clause is clearly highlighted using a red annotation to enhance interpretability.

Figure 7: Highlighting a non-matching clause with a red annotation.

An alternative query profile view provides a detailed, scaled rendering of the matching effectiveness of each clause using a form of Sankey diagram. The same left-to-right flow is used but connecting lines are added with thickness indicating the volume of matches produced by each clause.

This lower level feedback of matching information may only be of interest to the most detail-focused of human users but is useful context for AI agents that automate the formulation of complex queries.

3.6. AI-integration

3.6.1. Using AI to review results

The system provides a chat interface to allow patent searchers to ask questions about top-matching results and get answers from a choice of LLMs. The system has a few pre-canned questions for searchers lacking inspiration, such as one to request a feature comparison matrix for the inventions in the results.

Figure 8: LLM-produced feature comparison of dog lead patents - the LLM automatically inferred relevant feature dimensions from contextual input.

The system instructs the LLM to annotate any assertions used in its chat responses with citations (the blue links in the example). These citation lists are active elements in this system and when clicked, the system presents a modal interface displaying the referenced patents in detail. Users can then incorporate relevant attributes from selected documents into the query structure. This feature helps close the loop between the query builder and the LLM's interpretations of the information produced in results.

3.6.2. AI-assisted Iterative Query Development

Patent searchers do not like “black box” matching and want explainability in their queries which is why Boolean and keyword searches still dominate this space. However, an AI can be used to help a patent searcher define and refine such queries. The detailed types of information that the system can provide about search results for human users turns out to be useful context for an AI agent performing the same task of refining a query. The system can provide the usual top N ranked results with a total matched count but also significant keywords, a fully parsed query structure, worst N ranked results and detailed clause-level matching statistics.

The system can use an AI agent to help iteratively build Boolean queries for patents. In each iteration the LLM provides a structured query proposal and the system runs the query, returning detailed information about the results and effectiveness of the query clauses to the LLM for reconsideration.

The result of each iteration is that the LLM produces a new query tab with an editable variation of the query along with a human-readable description that clearly explains the refinements.

The LLM uses a combination of its own world-knowledge and detailed results from the search engine to revise queries.

Figure 9: An AI-generated query after a few iterations with highlighted rationale for the latest changes.

4. Discussion and Limitations

While the system remains a proof-of-concept without formal user studies or production deployment, it has been designed for compatibility with widely adopted scalable search technologies commonly used in large-scale patent information systems, thus ensuring a practical path to real-world applicability. Accessibility is a particular concern with graphical user interfaces: drag-and-drop interactions depend heavily on mouse input, so copy-and-paste functionality has been included to support keyboard-only users in selecting and repositioning clauses. Touch input is also supported for users on touchscreen devices such as mobile phones. Further work is needed to address additional accessibility challenges, including screen reader compatibility.

Finally, multi-lingual support presents another important consideration, as development to date has focused primarily on English content.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we presented FlowQuery, an innovative system designed to revolutionize patent search by integrating visual query formulation, AI-driven assistance, and transparency features. FlowQuery addresses longstanding challenges in patent information retrieval through a graphical Boolean query editor that simplifies the construction of complex queries. This visual interface, coupled with nested foldable logic containers, eliminates the ambiguity often associated with text-based systems, enabling users to craft precise searches intuitively. The system incorporates context-sensitive AI suggestions and clause-level matching feedback, enhancing query effectiveness while reducing cognitive load—improving usability without sacrificing legal defensibility essential for patent-related applications.

FlowQuery distinguishes itself through its seamless blend of structured and exploratory search capabilities. The drag-and-drop functionality allows users to refine queries directly from search results and semantic clusters, fostering an efficient discovery process. Interactive Sankey diagrams and detailed feedback mechanisms ensure transparency, providing an auditable trail of search logic that meets the stringent requirements of legal scrutiny. This combination of precision, flexibility, and accountability sets FlowQuery apart from traditional patent search tools.

The implications of FlowQuery extend beyond its immediate contributions. By streamlining patent search, it empowers users from legal professionals to inventors to navigate complex datasets with greater confidence and speed. Future research could expand clause types, integrating advanced machine learning for predictive query refinement, or developing collaborative search features. The LLM-generated feature comparison matrix is capable of adding structure to largely unstructured results and shows promise as a tool for enriching patent data for further analysis.

In conclusion, FlowQuery marks a significant advancement in patent search technology. Its emphasis on usability, transparency, and innovation not only addresses current limitations but also lays the groundwork for future developments. With potential applications in other domains requiring precise information retrieval, FlowQuery stands as a versatile and impactful tool, poised to reshape how we interact with complex data.

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